

1 **European Veterinary Immunology Workshop (EVIW) 2024:**
2 **tackling animal health within a One Health framework**

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21 Dedicated to the memory of Professor Simon Doherty, senior lecturer at Queen's University
22 Belfast and 'World Vet of the Year 2024' - a true ambassador for One Health.

23 **Abstract**

24 Animal health is a critical component of the One Health framework, which recognizes
25 the interconnectedness of human, animal, and environmental health. After a hiatus in in-person
26 meetings due to Covid-19, the European Veterinary Immunology Workshop (EVIW) was
27 convened in September 2024 to discuss the latest scientific discoveries of relevance to animal
28 health, to foster the development of new collaborative relationships, to support training and
29 capacity building in the multi-disciplinary skills and expertise required by the next generation
30 of animal immunologists. Against a backdrop of urgent global challenges inherent across
31 livestock production systems, experts from academia, industry partners and policy makers
32 united to share novel research findings, foster new collaborative initiatives and communicate
33 relevant ideas for improved targeting of infectious diseases. The broad impact that diseases in
34 animals can have across society illustrates how animal health plays an essential role in the One
35 Health framework by protecting human health, ensuring food safety, combating antimicrobial
36 resistance, and safeguarding the environment. Addressing animal health issues is therefore
37 crucial for a holistic and effective One Health approach to global health challenges.

38

39

40 **Introduction**

41 Amongst the greatest challenges we face are those related to the control of infectious diseases
42 which threaten animal health, food security and can pose a zoonotic risk to humans. Although
43 the exact number of pathogenic species is hard to quantify precisely as new pathogens are
44 identified and our understanding of existing ones deepens, it is estimated that approximately
45 60% of all known human infectious disease agents originate in animals, including *Brucella*,
46 HIV, *Salmonella*, and rabies virus and over 30 new human pathogens have been detected in
47 the last three decades, 75% of which have originated in animals (Jones et al., 2008). Given the
48 pressure to feed an expanding human population in the years ahead, it is a serious challenge to
49 avoid the infectious disease trap of animal agriculture (Hayek, 2022). The risk from which
50 extends from the farmyard to the backyard and into companion animals (Gamble et al., 2023;
51 Whitehead and Roberts, 2014). Due to global use (and misuse) of antibiotics, the WHO predicts
52 10 million deaths could be due to AMR by 2050 (Murray et al., 2022), and all stakeholders
53 involved in animal agriculture have an urgent responsibility to reduce our dependence on both
54 antibiotics and anthelmintics, with which increasing issues of resistance have been documented
55 on-farms. An estimated 20% of livestock production is lost to animal disease costing producers
56 over US\$300 billion every year (Analytica, 2021) and therefore the very sustainability of
57 animal production systems is under threat. From the wildlife perspective, the emergence of
58 avian influenza is already decimating wild bird populations and is now spreading to cows (Sah
59 et al., 2024), which is negatively impacting production, health and could potentially pose a risk
60 to humans. It is clear therefore that business as usual is not an option, urgent collective action
61 is required.

62 The One Health paradigm encompasses the interconnectedness of human health, animal
63 health, and the environment, advocating for interdisciplinary collaboration to address
64 multifaceted health challenges (Pitt and Gunn, 2024). Veterinary research plays a central role
65 in the One Health framework by elucidating zoonotic disease dynamics, monitoring emerging
66 infectious threats and advocating for sustainable environmental practices. The benefits of One
67 Health actions will be seen in the prevention of disease, enhanced food safety, a reduction in
68 antimicrobial usage and new tools for disease control in wildlife and vaccine development in
69 livestock and companion animals. Effective delivery on the promise of One Health depends on
70 collective action of all stakeholders across society including the consumer. It is within this
71 context that the EVIW 2024 was held to promote One Health awareness, to build collaborative
72 networks that will feed into pedagogy (Meade, 2023), to build the competencies required by

73 the next generation of animal health researchers (Frankson et al., 2016; Sobierajski et al., 2023;
74 Sreedharan and Nanni, 2019) and showcase the leading research taking place in animal health.

75 The in-person European Veterinary Immunology Workshop (EVIW) was held at the
76 Crowne Plaza Hotel in Dublin from the 4th-6th of September 2024 with the theme of ‘*Working
77 together, across continents, across specialties, across infectious agents and across species*’.

78 The theme was reflected in the participation of 7 keynote speakers from Ireland, the UK,
79 Switzerland and the USA (Table 1) and global participation across 26 countries (Table 2) with

80 The submitted abstracts were structured into the programme (Table 2) which informed the
81 major themes of the conference which were

- 82 • Grand Challenges
- 83 • Comparative Immunology, Immunogenetics and Genomics
- 84 • Immune models and Emerging technologies
- 85 • Infection and Immunity
- 86 • Mucosal Immunity and Vaccination
- 87 • Immunological toolbox and
- 88 • Future and One Health

89
90 Each session was led by at least 1 keynote speaker who discussed their research and outlined the
91 latest developments in their area. To set the scene, on day 1 of the conference, Professor Pat Wall from
92 UCD, uniquely qualified as both a medical doctor and veterinarian, emphasised the need for a renewed
93 focus on ‘health’ rather than ‘disease’ and reiterated the importance for collective action on diseases,
94 adding that “*We are all in the human health business*”. Following that, two speakers discussed cutting
95 edge research from human immunology (Professor Christoph Schiermann) as well as the reality of
96 work at the coalface of infectious diseases impacting humans and animals (Professor Delia Grace)
97 which illustrated the reality of the challenges we face as well as the potential of emerging science for
98 improved disease outcomes. Conference participants were joined by key experts in the animal health
99 policy, education and research sector to distil conference findings into implementation strategies for
100 the improved and effective targeting of animal diseases.

101 The conference ran over 3 days, and 190 delegates were registered for the conference. 26
102 countries were represented (Table 2), 143 abstracts were submitted, 84 posters were presented, 58 oral
103 presentations were given with 7 keynote speakers. The workshop also attracted 16 Industry sponsors
104 and exhibitors. Importantly, the conference was also attended by veterinary surgeons and other
105 regulatory authorities in national government departments.

106 A highlight of the workshop was the panel discussion before the close of the conference where
 107 policy makers engaged with scientists and keynote speakers to extract the relevance of immunological
 108 research for One Health policy. The conference also tackled future challenges in immunology,
 109 exploring how it can address emerging diseases and integrate new scientific tools into veterinary
 110 practice.

111 **Conference programme (Table 1)**

Day One	Session theme: Grand Challenges Chair Dr Kieran Meade
Professor Delia Grace UNITED KINGDOM	KEYNOTE TALK 1 The multiple burdens of zoonoses in low- and -middle income countries (LMICs): why zoonoses are worse for the poor
Professor Christoph Scheiermann SWITZERLAND	KEYNOTE TALK 2 Circadian rhythms and their importance in regulating the immune response
WELCOME RECEPTION & POSTER VIEWING	
Day two - AM	Session theme: Comparative Immunology, Immunogenetics and Genomics 1 Chairs: Dr Orla Keane IRELAND & Dr Preben Boysen NORWAY
Professor Cliona O'Farrelly IRELAND	KEYNOTE TALK 3 Comparative Immunology, Immunogenetics and Genomics
Femke Broere NETHERLANDS	Canine Immunology: Insights into Polarization of antigen presenting cells and T cell responsivity
Caroline Tafalla SPAIN	Teleost fish IgM+ plasma-like cells: beyond antibody secretion
Kristina Spariosu SERBIA	In vitro phagocytosis competition: a turtle, a goose and a dog – who has the best score?

Hege Lund NORWAY	Expanding the diagnostic toolbox in aquaculture: A case study of hemorrhagic smolt syndrome demonstrates the value of blood biochemistry analysis in farmed salmon
Zala Brajnik Kovačič SLOVENIA	Insight into genetic background of mastitis resistance in cattle: a comprehensive collection of candidate loci
Katarina Kotlaja SERBIA	The presence of chronic subclinical systemic inflammation during remission of canine atopic dermatitis
Carles Hernández-Banqué SPAIN	Genetic determinism of porcine plasma lipidome and its relationship to immunity
Teodor Jové Juncà SPAIN	Unveiling blood transcriptome regulatory variants involved in pig immunity
Laurent Gillet BELGIUM	A systems immunology approach reveals distinct roles of genetic and non-genetic factors in shaping variation of immune responses in cattle
Sabine Hammer AUSTRIA	Comparative analysis of swine leukocyte antigen (SLA) gene diversity in Göttingen Minipigs
Day two - AM	Session theme: Immune Models and Emerging Technologies Chairs: Stephanie Talker SWITZERLAND & Gregers Jungersen DENMARK
Cornelia Deeg ITALY	Immunocellular Dynamics and Metabolic Adaptations in Equine Recurrent Uveitis
Isabelle Schwartz FRANCE	Improving the early immune parameters of lung transplantation in the pig model by conditioning donors with corticosteroids
Sabine Hammer AUSTRIA	Exploring porcine models and MHC genetics in xenotransplantation

Christine Jansen NETHERLANDS	Developing a cell-based assay to study trained immunity in chicken NK cells
Emily Charlton UNITED KINGDOM	Modelling bovine tuberculosis infection in stem cell-derived macrophages
Kate Sutton UNITED KINGDOM	Chicken 3D enteroids as tool to determine virulence of non-notifiable avian influenza
Laura Miller USA	Comparative transcriptomic analysis of IAV infection in porcine organoids
Dirk Werling UNITED KINGDOM (virtual)	The use of precision-cut lung slices to assess Mycoplasma hyopneumoniae tissue interaction
Lonneke Vervelde NETHERLANDS	Chicken intestinal organoids: a novel method to measure the mode of action of feed additives
Robert Kammerer GERMANY	The TRDC-knockout pigs lacking $\gamma\delta$ T cells: an update
Day two - PM	Session theme: Infection and Immunity 1 Chairs: Kerstin Mair AUSTRIA & Femke Broere NETHERLANDS
Professor Elma Tchilian UNITED KINGDOM	Harnessing mucosal immunity: lesson from the pig model
Hans Nauwynck BELGIUM	Intriguing immune escape mechanisms developed by three animal viruses: equine herpesvirus 1, porcine reproductive and respiratory syndrome virus and feline enteric coronavirus
Thomas Démoulin SWITZERLAND	<i>Bos taurus</i> and <i>Bos indicus</i> cattle exhibit compelling different immune responses towards vector-borne viruses

Nadia Benjelloun UNITED KINGDOM	Moo-ving Beyond Allergies: Insight Into Cow Milk Allergy and a Potential Cure
Raquel Portugal UNITED KINGDOM	Protective immunization against genotype I of African swine fever virus using adenovirus vectored antigens
Sara Zaldivar Lopez SPAIN	miR-215 modulates inflammasome activation and autophagy during Salmonella infection in porcine intestinal cells
Larissa Oser GERMANY	Ascaris suum induces systemic T follicular helper type 2 cells, but only a weak Th2 response in growing pigs
Aida Tort SPAIN	Characterization of the immunostimulatory properties of a warthog microbiota component in porcine alveolar macrophages
Day two - PM	Session theme: Comparative Immunology, Immunogenetics and Genomics 2 Chairs: Eva Wattrang SWEDEN & ?
Stephanie Talker SWITZERLAND	Solving the puzzle of mononuclear phagocytes – species by species
Marta Alonso-Hearn SPAIN	Identification of deleterious genetic variants in the bovine transcriptome from Holstein cattle naturally infected with Mycobacterium avium subsp. Paratuberculosis
Piera Mazzone ITALY	Study of bovine immunopathogenetic pathways during Mycobacterium avium subsp. paratuberculosis infection in Marchigiana beef cattle a native Italian breed
Fany Blanc FRANCE	Immune traits are affected by genetic selection for faecal enterotypes in pigs
Mandeep Singh	Molecular characterization of immune related genes in native Poonchi chicken from Jammu, India

INDIA	
Robert Kammerer GERMANY	How to talk to the mother's immune system? Lessons from the foal
Melissa Stas AUSTRIA	PRRSV-induced T Cell Responses at the Maternal-Fetal Interface During Late Gestation
Day three - AM	Session theme: Mucosal Immunity and Vaccination Chairs: Gerald Barry IRELAND & Friedericke Ebner GERMANY
Professor Philip Griebel CANADA	KEYNOTE TALK 5 Understanding Mucosal Immunology to Enhance Vaccine Development
Tobias Kaeser AUSTRIA	Deciphering vaccine immunogenicity pigs promotes vaccine development for both pigs and humans
Hans Van der Weken BELGIUM	Targeted delivery of oral vaccine antigens to aminopeptidase N protects pigs against pathogenic E. coli challenge infection
Chidebere Ubachukwu UNITED KINGDOM	Evaluation of Live Attenuated Porcine Reproductive and Respiratory Syndrome Virus Vaccines Genetically Engineered to Express Peptide-based Immune Checkpoint Inhibitors
Sean Wattegedera UNITED KINGDOM	Humoral and cellular responses to a parapox virus-vectored antigen, potential for the development of a new vaccine to Chlamydia abortus
David Marín SPAIN	Identification of immune correlates of protection after intranasal vaccination with the attenuated African swine fever vaccine candidate BA71ΔCD2
Eliane Marti SWITZERLAND	Clinical improvement of equine insect bite hypersensitivity lesion scores following immunotherapy with Culicoides recombinant allergens in combination with a TLR-4 agonist

Sigridur Jonsdottir ICELAND	Can we treat allergy with transgenic barley?
Jeong In Yang DENMARK	Dissection of the antibody response to an antigen decorated VLP vaccine in rainbow trout
Gitte Erbs DENMARK	Design of a Porcine ETEC Multi Epitope Fusion Antigen vaccine
Day three - AM	Session theme: Infection and Immunity 2 Chairs: Milica Kovasevic SERBIA & Carolina Taffala SPAIN
Aude Remot FRANCE	Discovery of neutrophil subsets in cattle
Sabine Riffault FRANCE	The cytokine response to innate stimuli in blood of calves at birth and the occurrence of infectious diarrhoea
Giovanna De Matteis ITALY	Similarities and differences in the cellular immune response between healthy and naturally Mycobacterium bovis infected water buffaloes and cattle
Daniel Zaki UNITED KINGDOM	Identification and Characterisation of Porcine T Follicular Helper and T Follicular Regulatory Cells
Alexandra Correia PORTUGAL	Protection against the obligatory intracellular parasite Neospora caninum is dependent on IFN- γ signalling in myeloid and endothelial cells
Razieh Ardali SWITZERLAND	Muramyl di-peptide (MDP) is a potent inducer of “trained immunity” in porcine monocytic cells
Joshua Adjah GERMANY	Differential resistance to nematode infection is associated with the genotype- and agedependent pace of intestinal T cell homing

Artur Summerfield SWITZERLAND	Potent interferon-alpha responses against ASFV by plasmacytoid dendritic cells are STING pathway dependent and require tight junctions with infected macrophages
Anna Katharina Wunder AUSTRIA	Characterization of a novel marker staining memory subsets in porcine $\alpha\beta$ T cells in age- and antigen-specific context
Ulrike Blohm GERMANY	Virulent African swine fever virus infection of porcine monocytes leads to loss of ER function and subversion of SLA I
Day three - PM	Session theme: Future and One Health Chairs: Falko Steinbach UK & Kieran Meade IRELAND
Barry Rouse USA	KEYNOTE TALK 6 Meeting the challenge of controlling viral immunopathology
Michaela Wegg UNITED KINGDOM	Using deep learning to classify bovine retinal images into tuberculosis and non-tuberculosis disease states
Lisa Arnalot FRANCE	Innate Cytokine Profile and the link to fecal microbiota around calving in dairy cows
Simone Herel AUSTRIA	20-color flow cytometry in a veterinary species – yes, we can!
Day three - PM	Session theme: Immunological toolbox Chairs: Jayne Hope UK & Wilhelm Gerner UK
Crystal Loving USA (virtual)	What's in your toolbox? Immune reagent development for veterinary species
Gregers Jungersen DENMARK	Veterinary Toolkit. Isotype cross reactivity of anti-porcine IgG and IgA reagents

Alison Van Eenennaam USA	KEYNOTE TALK 7 Gene Editing Opportunities for Livestock Disease
Final discussion panel	Session theme: Future and One Health Chairs: Dr Simon Doherty, QUB, UK
	DISCUSSION ABOUT LESSONS AND IMPLICATIONS FOR POLICY Panellists: Prof Alison Van Eenennaam, USA Prof Grace Mulcahy, University College Dublin, Ireland Prof Delia Grace, UK Dr Caroline Garvan, DAFM, Ireland

112

113 A full list of submitted abstracts is available at the following link (EVIW, 2024).

114

115

116 **Professor Pat Wall** (University College Dublin) is a qualified medical doctor and veterinarian
 117 and in opening the EVIW 2024 outlined the importance of collective multi-disciplinary
 118 collaboration in One Health.

119

120 **Keynote speaker Professor Delia Grace Randolph** (University of Greenwich) used her keynote
 121 address to outline why zoonoses are worse for the poor and the urgency of the adoption of a One Health
 122 framework.

123

124

125 **Keynote speaker Professor Christoph Scheiermann** (University of Geneva) outlined his
 126 research elucidating the relevance of harnessing chronobiology for improved immune
 127 response outcomes – including for vaccination.

128

129

130 **Keynote speaker Professor Cliona O' Farrelly** (Trinity College Dublin) talked about her
 131 work across species and the valuable insights gained through comparative immunology of
 132 relevance to One Health.

133

134

135 **Keynote speaker Professor Philip Griebel (University of Saskatoon)** showcased his
 136 research on mucosal immunology and its relevance to vaccine design.

137

138

139 **Keynote speaker Professor Barry Rouse (University of Tennessee)** outlined his research
 140 regarding how to meet the challenge of controlling viral immunopathology.

141

142

143 **Keynote speaker Professor Alison Van Eenennaam** (University of California, Davis) outlines the

144 exciting progress for creating disease resistant livestock using gene editing.

145

146

EVIW Country Breakdown (Table 2)		
Country	Number	% of total
Ireland	26	13%
Austria	11	6%
Belgium	5	3%
Brazil	1	1%
Canada	4	2%
Czech Republic	3	2%
Denmark	4	2%
France	14	7%
Germany	18	10%
Hungary	1	1%
Iceland	2	1%
Italy	11	6%
Korea	1	1%
Netherlands	11	6%
Norway	4	2%
Pakistan	1	1%
Poland	1	1%
Portugal	3	2%
Scotland	1	1%
Serbia	5	3%
Slovenia	1	1%
South Korea	1	1%
Spain	14	7%
Sweden	3	2%
Switzerland	4	2%
United Kingdom	35	19%
United States	5	3%
Total	190	

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148

149

150 **The Future and One Health discussion panel** closed the EVIW 2024 with relevance for policy in
 151 terms of both education and practice. The panel was chaired by Dr Simon Doherty of QUB.

152

153 **Conference awards**

154 An important feature of the conference was the substantial support for the next generation of
 155 scientists. These awards were made possible by the generous funding from the Veterinary Immunology
 156 Committee (VIC) of the International Union of Immunological Societies (IUIS).

157 The oral talk and poster awards were awarded in honour of a pionerring veterinarian -
 158 the first woman to qualify as a veterinarian in Ireland – Aileen Cust and Irish scientist Professor
 159 William C. Campbell, who shared the 2015 Nobel Prize in physiology or medicine for helping
 160 discover the avermectin class of drugs commonly used in heartworm preventives and to treat
 161 parasitic infections in animals. The VIC supported three category of awards:

- 162 1. **Travel award recipients:** Dr Chidiebere Ubachukwu, Pirbright Institute; Nadia
 163 Benjelloun, Aberystwyth University; Simone Herel, University of Vienna, Katarina
 164 Kotlaja, University of Belgrade; Emily Charlton, The Roslin Institute
- 165 2. **Accessibiliy and inclusion award recipient:** Alexsander Moraes from the University
 166 of Sao Paulo, Brazil.
- 167 3. **Oral talk and poster prize recipients:** Sigridur Jonsdottir, University of Iceland and
 168 Melissa Stas, University of Veterinary Medicine Vienna, who were awarded the Aileen
 169 Cust and Professor William Campbell awards, respectively for talks. Julia Teresa Celis
 170 Moreno, Wageningen University and Hayley Brown, The Pirbright Institute, Surrey,

171 UK who were awarded the Aileen Cust and Professor William Campbell awards,
172 respectively for posters.

173 **Selected awardees of the Aileen Cust and and Professor William Campbell awards** (shown
174 LtoR were): Julia Teresa Celis Moreno, Wageningen University, Sigridur Jonsdottir,
175 University of Iceland and Alexsander Moraes from the University of Sao Paulo, Brazil. Awards
176 by Dr Simon Doherty, QUB and Dr Kieran Meade, UCD, Dublin.

177

178 **Policy implications and recommendations regarding One Health**

179 Another very useful outcome from EVIW 2024 was the discussion on the final day of the
180 conference with speakers and panellists from the Irish Department of Agriculture on the integration of
181 One Health into funding/policy and practice at Irish and EU levels. The inclusion of participants from
182 Northern Ireland made for an inclusive event which ties closely with the Irish Government Shared
183 Island approach to research and managing disease risk.

184 1. Emerging zoonoses –Professor Delia Grace:

- 185 i. In developing countries, human sickness is a major cause of falling into and remaining in
186 poverty and zoonoses are responsible for a substantial proportion of this.
- 187 ii. Emerging, zoonotic diseases are most important as global shocks and poverty traps
188 (situations where poverty persists because the poor lack the resources to escape it).
- 189 iii. Neglected, endemic zoonoses have higher health burden and more important poverty
190 impacts than emerging diseases.

- 191 iv. A relatively small number of diseases are responsible for most of the burden: classical,
192 emerging, foodborne.
- 193 v. Lack of good assessments of the multiple burdens of zoonoses hinders ability to manage
194 them.
- 195 2. The role of immunology – multiple speakers:
- 196 i. The advent of genomics technologies has enabled significantly enhanced understanding
197 of the immune system in non-model organisms including livestock.
- 198 ii. Many livestock models offer advantages in terms of understanding pathogens of interest,
199 including for influenza (e.g. pig model).
- 200 iii. Developing expertise in livestock immunology is a prerequisite toward enabling safer
201 food systems, underpinning the success of vaccination programmes and preventing the
202 spread of zoonotic diseases.
- 203 3. Genome editing –Professor Alison Van Eenennaam:
- 204 i. Genome editing is a very exciting natural technology which is being used in the USA to
205 create disease resistant livestock – e.g. For respiratory disease.
- 206 ii. Regulators in many countries consider simple edits (e.g. knockouts, moving allele
207 from one breed to another) with no “foreign DNA” to be “non-GMO” – unclear
208 currently what will happen from a regulatory perspective in the EU and/or UK.
- 209 iii. The fate of genome editing in livestock will depend upon developing a risk-based
210 regulatory framework that allows commercialization and trade of animal products
211 (meat, milk, eggs) and gametes.
- 212 4. Outcomes from panel discussion:
- 213 i. Animal health is a central pillar of One Health.
- 214 ii. Communication of the role of animal health more broadly is important.
- 215 iii. Impact of AI (artificial intelligence) on animal health will be momentous.
- 216 iv. Multidisciplinary integration is important to bridge the gaps and move scientists
217 out of sectoral silos. Working together leads to more impact.
- 218 v. The Irish government is moving quickly into the One Health space, with
219 overarching cross departmental and across agency panel as well as an all-island
220 One Health committee.
- 221 vi. A collective amnesia seems to be apparent coming out of Covid – existential
222 threat of emerging diseases potential to devastate human civilisation as more
223 pressure builds on wildlife and natural world.

- 224 vii. Ecosystem protection (as a pillar of One Health) is almost completely absent from
225 veterinary education.
- 226 viii. Might be useful to use pets as conduit for vaccination uptake in humans.
- 227 ix. A literate public is critical, groups pressure on policy makers.
- 228 x. Can we foster a new profession specialised in One Health?
- 229 xi. Can we implement One Health into curriculum at early school age?
- 230 xii. University college Dublin has developed a new One Health Centre – and this has
231 recently been designated as a World Health Organisation collaborating centre.
232 Useful template for other countries to follow and expand One Health connectivity.
233

234 **Conclusions and future directions**

235 The European Veterinary Immunology Workshop (EVIW) was held in Dublin in September
236 2024 with the theme of ‘*Working together, across continents, across specialties, across*
237 *infectious agents and across species*’. This theme reflects the urgent need for collective action
238 within a One Health framework to target the significant infectious disease challenges in animals
239 with potential consequences for food safety, security and human health (Editorial, 2023; Wang
240 et al., 2024). The workshop successfully achieved many objectives in terms of post-covid in
241 person networking, community building, education and training and policy connectivity. We
242 look forward to building on the success of EVIW 2024 at the EVIW 2027 in Vienna.
243

244 **Acknowledgements – sponsorship, funding and carbon offsetting**

245 The conference organisers would like to warmly acknowledge the sponsorship of the following
246 entities:

- 247 - The conference was co-funded by the OCED CRP. The OECD's Co-operative Research
248 Programme: Sustainable Agricultural and Food Systems (CRP) exists to strengthen
249 scientific knowledge and provide relevant scientific information and advice that will
250 inform future policy decisions related to the sustainability of agriculture, food, fisheries
251 and forests (www.oecd.org).
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259 keynote speaker.
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261 travel awards for young scientists attending EVIW 2024.
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263 The assistance of the conference organising company Keynote (www.keynotepco.ie) was also
264 greatly appreciated. Of note, attendees were offered the opportunity to provide a small
265 contribution to carbon offsetting due to flights and the money raised is being used to plant
266 native Irish trees on the Lyons University Farm of UCD, Dublin.

267

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